
Migration and Economic Development in Nigeria

Christopher N. Ekong¹, Okon J. Umoh², & Uduakobong E. Ukpe³

^{1,2,3}Department of Economics, University of Uyo

Abstract

The study investigated the effect of migration on economic development in Nigeria from 1981 to 2023. The study used human development index (HDI) to proxy economic development as the dependent variable while net migration rate (NETMIG), poverty (POV), foreign direct investment (FDI) and unemployment (UNEM) were used as the explanatory variables. Descriptive statistics, unit root test, bound cointegration test, as well as Autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) were employed to analyze the data. The study reveals that both in the short run and long run, net migration (NETMIG) had a negatively insignificant impact on economic development; in the short run and long run unemployment (UNEM) had a positive and significant impact on economic development. Also, in the short run, foreign direct investment (FDI) had a positive and significant impact on economic development in Nigeria while it had a negative and insignificant impact on economic development over the data period. The study thus concluded that migration did not promote economic development in Nigeria within the period under review. The study recommends that the Nigerian government should implement targeted migration policies to address specific needs of the country by improving infrastructural provision such as electricity, good roads, adequate pipe borne water etc. and government should improve on working conditions and wages to reduce the pull factor of better job opportunities.

Keywords:

Migration, Net Migration, Economic Development, Poverty, foreign direct investment, unemployment.

1. Introduction

The increasing waves of globalization, the first taking place between the second half of the last century and world war I, and the second which has occurred since World war II until today, implied an unprecedented flow of goods and factors across international borders. The first episode of mass migration dates back to the nineteenth century, when millions of individuals flew to the New World. This phenomenon, taking place along with the first wave of globalisation, was absolutely massive: approximately 50 million of Europeans fled from their home country to the New World, between 1820 and 1913 (Hatton and Williamson, 2003). Ever since, aside from a halt in the period between the two World Wars, international migration has accompanied the reprise of the globalisation process, while areas of origin and destination of migration have varied and expanded.

In particular, strong flows of labour force migrants from the less developed to more industrialized countries have become a widespread phenomenon, despite the fact that the

constraints due to migrant policies may have suppressed a vast amount of potential migration that otherwise would have taken place. In the recent thirty years, indeed, international mobility has not kept the pace of the other two indices of globalisation, namely international trade and mobility of capital, although migration pressure does not seem to have declined. In fact, whereas, in the first wave of globalisation, mobility of labour did not suffer from particular restrictions from the receiving countries, the last thirty years have indeed witnessed a growing institutional and legislative firmness on restricting access and on selecting foreign workers, in particular in Europe. Yet, considering the queues of applicants for regular immigration permits in the developing world, the surge in illegal immigration and the increasing number of those that seek asylum in the developed world (Hatton and Williamson, 2003) as a proxy of migration pressure, all these indices point in the direction of increasing rather than declining pressure.

The mobility of the population has been an inseparable part of human existence since the days of civilization. Human migration is not a new phenomenon. Migration has been a component of man's existence from the beginning of time. The concept of migration stretches back to the commercial era, when European migrants travelled to Africa via merchant capitalism to obtain protectorates and dwell in vast tracts of territory for more than 300 years (Golden and Reinert, 2006). Furthermore, according to the National Geographic Society (2005), migration has occurred throughout human history, beginning with the journeys of the first tribes of humans in East Africa to their current location in the universe.

Migration is the movement of people from one geographical location to another which may be temporary or permanent in nature Amrevurayire and Ojeh (2016). Migration which has been part of human existence occurs as a result of prevailing conditions and the reasons for it differ from one migrant to another depending on the prevailing circumstances that triggered the migrant's decision. Man has been on the move since creation in quest for survival and to exploit both the physical and socio-economic opportunities in his environment for his wellbeing. Migrants have also been compelled to migrate from their usual place of abode in the face of environmental challenges such as flooding, desertification, earthquakes, and similar environmental inconveniences. The enormity of global migration has made it the primary policy priority of practically every government in both emerging and established economies. The International Organization for migration (IOM) states that migration can be described as: A process of relocating, either over an international boundary or inside a State. It is a population movement that comprises any type of human mobility, regardless of its length, composition, or causes; it includes migration of refugees, displaced people, uprooted people, and economic migrants (IOM, 2004).

Nigeria plays an important role in African migration and other parts of the world. As the most populous African country, Nigeria has become increasingly involved in international migration to Europe, Gulf countries and South Africa. The economic reasons for migration in most cases are related to wage differentials, differences in GDP per capita, large economic disparities among regions and also unemployment differentials (Afaha, 2018). Moreover, there is continuing debate about the impact of international migration on the sending and receiving countries as well as on the migrants themselves.

In relating migration to economic development in Nigeria, it can be inferred that since time immemorial, the relationship between migration and development of any type has remained a topical issue under serious academic debate and as such, the movement of people from one settlement to another, apparently in search of a better life is not a novel phenomenon.

Experiences have however shown that what is commonly obtainable is the increasing voluntary movement and perceived forceful movement of people of low-skill and low-wage as well as high-skill and high-wage from less developed rural areas to a more developed urban area, (Jacob, 2007). The truth is that, throughout all ages, migration, which is the movement of people, animals and even goods from one place to another, has been in existence. And that is why Hall (2010) posits that migration has been a key human response to environmental, social, political, economic and structural changes.

Economic growth and development often lead to migration in search of better education, employment, health, infrastructural facilities, investment and better life. In many development research publications, it is argued that migration leads to industrialization and economic growth taking into account the experiences of the developed world in 19th and early 20th century. There is a negative relationship between uncoordinated and unplanned migration and sustainable development. Rapid migration rate if left unplanned as per the experiences of many developing countries often leads to unsustainable development and rise in poverty, crime and insecurity in towns and cities. One of the continent's main developmental challenges for the first two decades of this millennium would be how to successfully manage its urbanization for sustainable economic development. (Falade, 2005).

However, insecurity is another factor that has intensified the rate of human migration among other factors in Nigeria. It is a universal human instinct to seek survival and better life which leads people to migrate with the perception that developed nations are more secured. Insecurity and fear of kidnapping, herdsmen attack and boko haram insurgents has made many people to migrate, which further worsen the infrastructural gap in urban areas where the available social amenities are stretched, people become homeless and unemployment becomes intensified with crime being the order of the day.

People movement from less developed to developed nations has been regarded as one of the challenges to achieving of development efforts of the cities and the nation at large. Simultaneously, the Nigerian government is not left out of this quagmire, because the best brains are seen moving out to seek for better living conditions and improved infrastructure. Hence there is evidence on how migration affects poverty along different dimensions. Migration may impose a high cost for developing countries like Nigeria by leaving the country without the human capital necessary to achieve long-term economic growth. This human capital flight may impose a significant economic burden for developing countries as migrants take with them the value of their training, which is often subsidized by governments with limited resources. While migration impacts development, economic conditions are important drivers of migration. People migrate for a variety of reasons including the search for better economic opportunities, education, family reunion and escaping violence. People often migrate for a combination of these and other reasons. However, the expected income gap between developed and developing countries is a strong incentive for people to migrate (Czaika and de Haas 2011a). As such, migration affects development, but development also affects migration. To this end, the study seeks to examine the impact of migration on economic development in Nigeria,

In Nigeria, study conducted by Pew Research Centre shows that Nigeria tops chart of people who plan to move to another country within the next 5 years with 48%, among the 12 countries sampled for the survey. According to data from the World Migration Report (2020),

there were 272 million international migrants worldwide in 2019. (McAuliffe and Khadria, 2019). This accounts for 3.5% of the world's population. Furthermore, in terms of gender, 52% and 48% of international migrants were male and female, respectively. In addition, 74% of overseas migrants were between the ages of 20 and 64. Furthermore, with 17.5 million migrants, India was the top country of origin for international migrants. Mexico comes in second and China comes in third, with 11.8 million and 10.7 million overseas migrants, respectively. However, with 50.7 million international migrants, the United States remained the biggest country of destination for international migrants.

Nigeria has experienced large internal and external migration flows in the last decades. In the 1970s, the oil boom attracted foreigners, and the country saw more people immigrating than emigrating. However, in the 1980s, the number of Nigerians leaving the country increased as a consequence of the economic downturn and political instability. Since then, the net migration rate has stayed negative. With 206 million people, Nigeria has, nonetheless, the largest population in Africa and the seventh largest in the world.

As a result, the investigation into the effect of migration on economic development in Nigeria was motivated by the need to understand the various push and pull forces responsible for the country's high rate of external migration. Understanding the root causes of international migration and depicting the various repercussions of external migration in Nigeria would help guide policy decisions and provide insights into the best economic development plans. Despite several efforts by the Federal, State, and Local governments, Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs), and other stakeholders to stem the unceasing stream of migration in Nigeria, the situation has persisted. Despite the hurdles of international migration, Nigerians have continued to relocate to economically stable economies around the world in search of economic opportunities to support themselves and their dependents at home. Low-intensity warfare, insufficient economic possibilities, and a huge young population has resulted in a large number of irregular migrants attempting to embark on the perilous journey to Europe from Nigeria.

It is against this backdrop, that the study would investigate the impact of migration on economic development in Nigeria. In line with this position, the study attempted to provide answers to the following questions:

What is the impact of migration on economic development in Nigeria? To what extent does migration affect economic development in Nigeria?

Specifically, the research questions are:

- i. What is the relationship between migration and economic development in Nigeria?
- ii. Does migration impact on economic development in Nigeria?

The broad objective of this study is to examine the impact of migration on economic development.

Specifically, this study seeks to;

- i. Investigate the relationship between migration and economic development
- ii. Examine the effect of migration on unemployment.

The study is important considering the attendance impact of migration challenges facing the Nigerian economy and emphasis on multidimensional poverty rate occasion by the high unemployment and inflation caused by the migration syndrome in recent times. The findings of this study will benefit the government, policy makers, stakeholders, students and researchers. It will provide some insight for policy makers and the government on how to promote employment opportunities to mitigate the incessant migration syndrome, checking and developing infrastructure facilities so as to reduce poverty, unemployment and enhance human capital development in Nigeria. It will equally help them to strengthen the quality of policy made for sustainable economic development. The study is an addition to the existing empirical literature on migration and economic development in Nigeria. Therefore, the study will serve as a referral document for prospective researchers and students in economics and other related disciplines.

The study covers the period between 1981 to 2023. Within this period, Nigeria witnessed poor growth and development, high migration rate, high unemployment rate, high poverty rate and low level of economic development. Though diverse indices of measuring economic development have been explored, the study only focuses on one of the core index for development which is human capital development index. The index so selected is adequate since it incorporates health, education, life expectancy and improved standard of living and other social indicators that could characterize the economic development of a nation.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Conceptual Literature

2.1.1 Concept of Economic Development:

Economic development is seen as a process whereby simple, low-income national economies are transformed into modern industrialized economies. Although the term is sometimes used as a synonym for economic growth, generally it is employed to describe a change in a country's economy involving qualitative as well as quantitative improvements.

There are various views to what economic development, some development expert sees economic development as a wider or broader concept than growth, to then it is taken to mean growth plus change. It is growth accompanied with structural transformation. It is related to qualitative changes in economic wants, goods, incentives, institutions, productivity and knowledge or the upward movement of the entire social system. It describes the underlying determinants of growth such as technological and structural changes. In fact, economic development embraces both growth and non-growth dimensions. An economy can grow but it may not develop because poverty, unemployment and inequalities may continue to persist due to the absence of technological and structural changes (Jhingan 2007).

Economic development are programmes, policies or activities that seek to improve the economic well-being and quality of life for a community. Economic development also implies economic growth plus progressive changes in certain important variables which determines the well – being of people. It is the process by which emerging economies become advanced economies also the process were countries with low living standards become nations with high living standards

It also implies that the overall health, well-being, and academic level of the general population improves in that economy. Economic development also fosters innovation and technological advancements, leading to the creation of new industries and job opportunities.

Economic Development is the development of economic wealth of countries, regions or communities for the well-being of their inhabitants (Salmon, 2011). From the policy viewpoint, Economic Development can be referred to as efforts that seek to improve the economic well-being and quality of life for a community by creating and/or retaining jobs and supporting or growing incomes and the tax base (Salmon, 2011). The scope of economic development includes the process and policies by which a nation improves the economic, political and social well-being of its people (O'Sullivan & Sheffrin). This study used human development index (HDI) to measure economic development.

2.1.2 Concept of Migration

Migration is the movement of people from one place to another with the intentions of settling permanently or temporarily in a new location. These movements can be driven by various factors including economic, social, political or environmental motivations. Migration can be international movement where migrants move from one country to another or internal movement within a country often from rural to urban areas. (Ravenstein,1885). Immigration and emigration are the concepts that describe migration. Immigration refers to the act of moving from one country to another, to settle or reside there permanently or for long period of time. This involves crossing international borders to enter a new country, often with the intention of seeking better economic opportunities, fleeing persecution or conflict, or reuniting with family members. Then Emigration is the act of leaving one's own country to settle in another country, typically for an extended period or permanently. This involves crossing international borders to exit one's home country, often in search of better economic opportunities, education, or personal freedom

2.2 Theoretical framework

2.2.1 Human Capital Theory

Human Capital Theory (HCT) was developed by Gary Becker, Jacob Mincer, and Theodore Schultz in 1954. Who posits that individuals' knowledge, skills, and experiences are key assets that contribute to economic productivity, meaning that investment in education, training and health care secures individual's productivity. This theory, revolutionized the way we think about labor, education, and economic growth.

At its core, HCT asserts that human beings are not just passive recipients of wages, but rather active investors in their own human capital. This capital encompasses various attributes, such as education, training, health, and experience, which can be acquired and developed through deliberate investments of time, money, and effort. According to HCT, individuals make rational decisions about investing in their human capital, weighing the costs and benefits of acquiring new skills, knowledge, and experiences. This investment process is driven by the expectation of future returns, such as higher earnings, better job prospects, and improved career advancement opportunities.

2.2.2 Neoclassical Theory of Migration:

The Neoclassical theory of Migration was propounded by Todaro in 1969 and Harris & Todaro in 1970. This theory of Migration was the first theoretical basis formulated to describe labour migration. The theory observes migration as the end result of geographic differences between supply and demand of labour. These differences exist globally. Neoclassical theory expressed that international migration arises due to variances in wage levels between countries and labour markets. According to this theory, labour migration would stop if wage discrepancies were eliminated. The principle suggests that wage variations between regions are the foremost cause for labour migration. Neoclassical theory proposes that global migration was tied to the demand and supply of labour in the world. Nations with labour shortages and excessive demand will have high wages that will attract immigrants from countries with excess workforce. The main premise of the neoclassical theory of migration is directed by the push factors that push the person to leave their place of origin and by the pull factors that lead them to move to destination country. Neoclassical theory concluded that the main causes of migration are different wages and access to work (Sjaastad, 1962; Todaro, 1976).

The neoclassical theory of migration was divided into two main classes, such as macroeconomic and microeconomic aspects. At the macro level, neoclassical economic theory states that the sole purpose of migration is the exceptional imbalance in the supply of labour, the demand for labour, which leads to wage discrepancies in different countries. The macro level principle suggests that labour changes are due to differentials of wages, from low wage regions to regions with excessive wages, and that capital will go in the opposite direction. Migration will progressively decrease the workforce at the destination of the sending end. Countries with low wages have a much wider range of people, and as a result the large labour supply results to low wages. High-wage nations have surprisingly greater capital, which is often the reason why capital will shift to high-wage nations with low wages and manpower. When this movement occurs, wages go to a shared level. In the long term, based on neoclassical theory, migration flow will be minimized due to the fact that income convergences will decrease inducements to migrate (De Haas, 2008; Fagerheim, 2015).

At the micro level, the neoclassical principle of migration considers migrants as a person with coherent actions, with the purpose of going deep into the thought of cost-benefit migration. When there are free choice and full access to information, they move to the areas where they can be most creative, that is, the region where they can earn the highest wages. This significant mobility is based on the precise abilities a man or woman possesses and, moreover, on the unique structure of the labour markets. The micro point of view of neoclassical explains migration through a cost-benefit exploration, as human beings desire to maximize their non-public income. People think about their net-return on migration before making a choice. If the threat of getting a job and expected income in remote places extends beyond the rate of migration and the acceptance of opportunities, the individual may also find it extremely good to migrate. But because of the desire of the individual at the micro level, different individuals have clear expectations on migration (Massey, 1993; de Haas, 2008). According to the neoclassical view of migration, the workforce is moving from places with low global wages to countries with especially excessive wages due to wage variation between countries. Remittances provide a means of poverty reduction and development of economy when immigrants send remittances to their homeland. On the other hand, this type of migration

to distant places could damage the development and growth when the homeland loses relatively skilled workers, known as Brain Drain. Therefore, human capital losses can adversely affect growth of the economy, as indicated in the principles of neoclassical (Fagerheim, 2015).

2.2.3 New Economics of Labour Migration Theory:

The New Economics of Labour Migration theory emerged in the 1990s as a fundamental response to previous migration theories, especially neoclassical ones. New Economics of Labour Migration, which presumably sought to correct to each of the structural emphasis of the historical-structural point of view and the theoretical insufficiencies of the neoclassical theoretical framework (Stark, 1991; Massey, 1993; Taylor, 1999; Taylor & Martin, 2001; de Haas, 2008). The essence of this principle is that migration selection is no longer a character choice. It is a collective selection made by migrant families. Migration choices are made to maximize household income, as well as to reduce the dangers and alleviate the constraints associated with market failures. Remittances can serve as an insurance plan for future risks, as the home depends on unique sources of income. Remittances are also considered as financing capital when there is no access to credit facilities in the homeland (Massey, 1993; Taylor & Martin, 2001; de Haas, 2008).

The idea of the New Economics Labor Migration system relating to Oded Stark's work is considered a criticism of the micro model of the neoclassical principle which conceptualizes migration as a decision of character. According to Stark (1991), migration can be a device used by households to maximize profits and it represents a significant source of income. By sending your loved one away from home, a family gets a loan that they will pay until migrants record their earnings later. They believed that if humans migrate to increase their income, they must send remittances to their homes (Taylor, 1999). NELM theory adapts to the Nigerian situation in which a family gather resources to send a member out of the country with a declared agreement and expectation to remit to their homes (Massey, 1993). Stark and Lucas (1988) stressed that there's a specific and contractual agreement between each family members and the migrant before migration occurs.

2.3 Empirical Literature

There has been plethora of literature on migration and economic growth, but little has been done on migration and economic development. Various arguments have been advanced as to the impact of migration and economic development, while some argue that migration does not have any significant effect on economic development others affirm that migration has a significant impact on economic growth and development. In line with this view, Adaja et al (2022) examined harnessing the migration and development nexus for sustainable development in Nigeria using descriptive analysis and it shows that more than a billion people rely on international and internal migrants to escape poverty, economic shock, improved health, education and economic status of their family and communities. This marks a change from the days when migration was seen as a failure of development but rather as an engine of poverty reduction. The huge amount of remittances from migrants has been yielding considerable benefits for promoting sustainable development. There is therefore the need by the government to harness the gains of remittances by coming up with policies that would favour migration and eliminate discrimination against migrants. Protecting the rights of migrants will reap bigger

gains for sustainable development, especially in developing countries. Therefore, this paper explores the relevance of migration to sustainable development in Nigeria.

Also, Faruk et al, (2022) investigated net migration and economic growth nexus: empirical evidence from Nigeria, using time series secondary data spanning the period of 1970 to 2017, applying the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) Bounds testing approach. The results of the co-integration test show that, there is a long run co-integrating relationship between net migration and economic growth alongside other control variables. Specifically, the findings of the study revealed a negative significant long run relationship between net migration and economic growth. Therefore, the study recommends that the push factors such as poor wage and incentive structure in Nigeria need to be addressed. Moreover, the pull factors, such as good quality of life abroad need to be provided in Nigeria, in order to discourage people from leaving the country. The latter can be achieved through massive infrastructural development, transparent recruitment process and incentive based remuneration system that rewards achievement and hard work.

Similarly, Duru (2021) examined the leading causes and consequences of international migration in Nigeria. The data was collected through a structured questionnaire. The opinions of 100 respondents selected through the purposive sampling technique were obtained on the principal causes and consequences of international migration in Nigeria. The findings revealed that the principal causes of international migration in Nigeria were job opportunities, unemployment, wealth prospects, safety and security, better conditions of service, low salaries and higher standards of living. These foremost causes of international migration in Nigeria were mostly economic factors. Furthermore, the findings showed that the foremost positive and negative effects of international migration in Nigeria were integrated development, increase in remittances, cheap and surplus labour, urban services and social infrastructure under stress, stricter immigration norms, multi-ethnic society and increased tolerance, Xenophobia, close gaps in skills and cultural dilution. These effects were economic, social and political. Among others, the study, thus, recommends that: the strategies of the government for stemming international migration should address push factors of unemployment, safety and security and low salaries and pull factors such as job opportunities, wealth prospects, better conditions of service and higher standards of living since they are the root causes of international migration. Furthermore, migration, a long-standing poverty reduction and strategy for human development need to be mainstreamed into policies of development in Nigeria at the Federal, State and Local Governments.

In line with Duru et al proposition, Kunwar (2021) studied the impacts of migration on poverty reduction at individual, households, community and national level. Both internal and international migration phenomenon including working environment of migrants are analyzed. The paper is based on secondary sources of information with aim of find evidence on linkages between migration and poverty at individual, household and community and National levels. Migration phenomenon has shown the evidences of in reducing poverty level but migrants are being compelled to work in an exploitative and unhygienic environment. Female migrants are being more victims of exploitation than male migrants. The poverty reduction has been gained in return of exploitative and health hazards working environment of migrants can be considered as an injustice to migrants and their place of origin as well as countries of origin.

Further, Adeseye (2021) examined migrants' remittance and economic growth in Nigeria. Remittance inflow was used as dependent variable and gross domestic products, inflation, imports and exports were independent variables. In this study, secondary data were utilized. The study employs annual data obtained from world development and international financial statistics which covers the period of 29 years (1990-2018). Quantitative data collected were evaluated through descriptive statistics; and the hypotheses formulated were tested with the use of multiple linear regressions which includes ANOVA, Correlation, and Coefficient. From the findings of the study and the tested hypotheses, it was discovered that significant relationship exists between remittance and gross domestic product, exports and imports in Nigeria while inflation has no significant relationship with remittance. The study therefore proffers some recommendations towards utilizing the influx of remittance for economic growth in Nigeria.

To further buttress Adeseye (2021) view, Škuflić and Vučković (2018) analysed the effects of emigration on emigrant countries' unemployment rates (short-term effect) in selected EU emigrant countries. The panel data analysis (fixed-effects model) covers the period from 2004 to 2015, and a total of nine EU countries: Bulgaria; Estonia; Greece; Croatia; Latvia; Lithuania; Poland; Portugal; and Romania. The obtained results show that emigration increases the unemployment rate in emigrant countries confirming that, besides generally expected positive effects in terms of a fall in unemployment, emigration could also have an adverse effect on emigrant countries' labour markets. Such results point to structural issues in the labour market caused by emigration, i.e., an increase in the labour supply and demand mismatch, which is discussed in the paper through the descriptive analysis of Job Vacancy Rate (JVR) data.

More so, Ojo (2016) examined selected publications of scholars and harnessed their perspectives on the impact of immigration on Nigerian economy. The findings show that immigration is traceable to presence of factor endowment such as crude oil and insufficient manpower in some areas like technology, medicine, agriculture etc. Immigration has contributed to growth of gross domestic product via filling the capacity gap. However, there are negative impacts that come through diffusion such as swallowing up cultural heritage, transfer of diseases and such like.

Ratha *et al.* (2014) provided a review of the literature on the development impact of migration and remittances on origin countries and on destination countries in the South. International migration is an ever-growing phenomenon that has important development implications for both sending and receiving countries. For a sending country, migration and the resulting remittances lead to increased incomes and poverty reduction, and improved health and educational outcomes, and promote economic development. Yet these gains might come at substantial social costs to the migrants and their families. Since many developing countries are also large recipients of international migrants, they face challenges of integration of immigrants, job competition between migrant and native.

Troshchenkov (2011) examined the influence of immigration on the unemployment rate in 99 municipalities of Denmark during three years. Most of American studies showed neutral or positive effect of immigration on unemployment of the native population, but many European studies find negative effects of immigration. The study used a regression model in order to analyze and draw conclusions from effect of immigration on the unemployment rate

in Denmark, paying particular attention to immigrants from non-Western countries. The results indicate that changes in the foreigner population and in population with non-Western origins do not lead to the significant changes in the unemployment rate. Hereby, it could be stated that derived conclusions are comparable and consistent with underlying theory and previous study.

2.4 Summary of Literature Reviewed and Research Gap:

A number of research has been conducted on migration and economic growth, yet limited attention has been given to the nexus between migration and economic development in Nigeria. A number of scholars have explored this relationship using various research methods and techniques in analyzing the relationship between migration and economic development.

These scholars include Adaja et al (2022), Faruk et al, (2022) and Adeseye (2021) among others. These studies employed different techniques such as Multivariate analysis, descriptive analysis, multi-staged sampling technique and ANOVA tests to examine the interactions among these variables. Furthermore, studies like, Ojo (2016) have employed econometric and descriptive techniques in analyzing the relationship between migration and economic development.

Studies such as Škuflić and Vučković (2018), examined the causes and effects of emigration on emigrant countries' unemployment rates (short-term effect) in selected EU emigrant countries. Within the Nigerian context, the research reveals a nuanced and sometimes contradictory understanding of migration and economic Development. For example, Adaja et al (2022), establish that majority of the migrants migrated to escape poverty, economic shock, improved health, education and economic status of their family and communities. On the other hand, Duru (2021) revealed that the major causes of international migration in Nigeria were job opportunities, unemployment, wealth prospects, safety and security, better conditions of service, low salaries and higher standards of living.

This divergence in findings highlights a gap in understanding the main reason for migration through which migration influence economic development in Nigeria, particularly examining the effect of migration on unemployment. Data gap also observed in the literature is that most of the studies reviewed used survey method and descriptive technique to analyze the relationship between migration and economic development. In this study, annual time series was used to investigate the relationship between migration and economic development in Nigeria. It is also evident from the literature that through some level of work has been done on migration and economic development but the variable used differs

Also the study used the autoregressive distributive lag (ARDL) model as its estimation technique. This study therefore used time series data and different measures of migration and economic development variables like Unemployment (UNEM), net migration rate (NETMIG), foreign direct

investment (FDI), human development index (HDI), poverty (POV) to provide evidence of the relationship between migration and economic development in Nigeria,

3. Research Methodology

This section explains the methodology and data used in the study. Data for the study were collected from secondary sources from various publications of Central Bank of Nigeria, National Bureau of Statistics and World Development Indicator (WDI). Therefore, the study adopts expo facto (after the fact) to investigate the effect of migration on economic development in Nigeria

3.1 Research Design

The study used an ex-post facto research approach to assess the relationship between migration and economic development in Nigeria from 1981 to 2023. The ex post facto research design is a type of non-experimental research design that looks at the relationship between two variables (independent and dependent) that have already occurred or existed. In other words, the researcher has no control over the variables because they have already occurred, and the study is conducted after the fact. The focus of the study is to investigate the relationship between migration and economic development in Nigeria.

3.2 Model Specification

The model for this study is specified as follows:

3.1.1 Migration and Economic development equation:

The functional form of the model for migration and economic development equation for this study is specified as:

$$HDI=f(POV, NETMIG, FDI, UNEM,) \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

The econometric form of the model is given as:

$$HDI_t = a_0 + a_1POV_t + a_2NETMIG_t + a_3FDI_t + a_4UNEM_t + U_t\dots\dots (2)$$

$$(-) \quad (- +) \quad (+) \quad (-)$$

Linearizing it we have:

$$\log HDI_t = \log a_0 + a_1\log POV_t + a_2\log NETMIG_t + a_3\log FDI_t + a_4\log UNEM_t + U_t \dots\dots (3)$$

HDI_t – Human development index in time t

POV_t – Poverty in time t

NETMIG—Net migration in time t

FDI_t -- Foreign Direct Investment in time t

UNEM_t – Unemployment rate in time

U_t – Error term

Table 1: Data Description and Sources

S/N	Variables	Description of Data	Source
1	UNEM (%)	Unemployment rate is the rate that expresses the total number of people in the labour markets who are willing and able to work at the prevailing wage rate but could not be employed. It is used as one of the explanatory variable in the model	WDI (2023)
2	NETMIG (%)	Net migration is the difference between the number of people entering a country (immigrants) and those leaving (emigrants) a country during a given period. It is a proxy for migration and is used as an explanatory variable in the model.	WDI (2023)
3	HDI (%)	Human development index is the index of health, life expectancy and education a nation holds. It is proxy for economic development and it is used as dependent variable in the model.	WDI (2023).
4	POV (%)	This represents the rate of poverty. This study adopts consumption expenditure per capita as measure of poverty because there is existing data on the variable, and it is assumed that people consume more of their income leaving little proportion for savings and investment.	World Development Indicator (2023)
5	FDI (%)	FDI stands for Foreign Direct Investment . It refers to an investment or business interest made by companies or individuals located in another country. This typically involves acquiring ownership or control over a company, establishing new operations, or expanding existing business activities.	World Development Indicator (2023)

4.0 RESULTS PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

4.1 Descriptive statistics and matrix of correlations

Table 2: Descriptive statistics

	HDI	POV	NETMIG	FDI	UNEM
Mean	0.442791	237905.6	29596.30	1.484884	12.09535
Median	0.430000	59005.50	64163.00	1.090000	10.60000
Maximum	0.520000	3867534.	145575.0	5.790000	32.50000
Minimum	0.380000	214.4000	-507539.0	0.260000	1.900000
Std. Dev.	0.048664	594716.8	107585.2	1.192673	8.393080
Skewness	0.260951	5.459743	-3.019366	1.888915	0.674012
Kurtosis	1.489218	33.83883	15.50208	6.697598	2.411323
Jarque-Bera	4.577430	1917.565	345.3765	50.06675	3.876644

Probability	0.101397	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.143945
Sum	19.04000	10229941	1272641.	63.85000	520.1000
Sum Sq. Dev.	0.099465	1.49E+13	4.86E+11	59.74367	2958.639
Observations	43	43	43	43	43

Source: Researchers' Computation.

The descriptive statistics of the variables are presented in Tables 2 above. This table highlight key trends in Nigeria's economic indicators during the review period. The data reveal a high level of poverty (POV), unemployment (UNEM) and net migration (NETMIG). For poverty (POV), the mean, median, and maximum values are 237905.6, 59005.50 and 3867534.0, respectively. Net migration (NETMIG) statistics include a mean of 29596.30, a median of 64163.00, and a maximum of 145575.0, for unemployment, 12.09535 (mean), 10.60000 (median) and 32.50000 (maximum) respectively.

In contrast, variables such as foreign direct investment (FDI) made relatively low contributions to economic development in the period under review. This is evidenced by the statistics of FDI, with the mean value of 1.484884, the median is 1.090000, and the maximum is 5.790000 respectively.

The effect of the volatile nature of explanatory variables; poverty (POV), foreign direct investment (FDI) and unemployment rate (UNEM) to economic development during the period suggest that economic development responses to the cyclical fluctuations or changes in these variables. This is revealed by the Poverty (POV) statistics with the mean of 237905.6, a median of 59005.50, a maximum of 3867534.0, and a standard deviation of 594716.8. Foreign direct investment (FDI) has a mean of 1.484884, a median of 0.090000, a maximum 5.790000 and a standard deviation of 1.192673 and for unemployment (UNEM) statistics include a mean of 12.09535, a median of 10.60000 and a maximum of 32.50000, with a standard deviation of 8.393080 respectively.

4.1.1 Skewness and Kurtosis Analysis:

The skewness results indicate that two variables are positively skewed, suggesting right-tailed distributions. The kurtosis results show that foreign direct investment (FDI), poverty rate (POV), and net migration (NETMIG), are leptokurtic (kurtosis > 3), indicating peaked distributions. Conversely, human development index (HDI), unemployment rate (UNEM) are platykurtic (kurtosis < 3), reflecting flatter distributions.

4.1.2 Normality and Variability:

The Jarque-Bera test confirms that all variables are normally distributed over the analysis period. The standard deviation values highlight the extent of variation in the data, with most variables showing significant deviations from their true values.

Econometric interpretation:

The analysis therefore shows that in the period under review, poverty (POV), net migration (NETMIG), and unemployment (UNEM), were on the increase, therefore exhibiting a considerable impact on economic development, this is evidenced by the statistics of POV, 237905.6 for mean, 59005.50 for median and a maximum of 3867534.0 while NETMIG has a statistics of 29596.30 for mean, 64163.00 for median and a maximum of 145575.0 and for

UNEM, 12.09535 for mean, 10.60000 for median and a maximum of 32.50000. More so, FDI which is supposed to impact the economic development positively was rather low (with mean, median and maximum of 1.484884, 1.090000 and 5.790000) as its contribution to economic development in the period under review was not felt and therefore reduces the investment portfolio of both the foreigners and locals alike. This maybe cause by the socio- economic problems such as banditry, government fiscal policy on taxation, political turmoil and insecurity.

Table 3: Correlation Matrix

	HDI	POV	NETMIG	FDI	UNEM
HDI	1				
POV	0.35	1			
NETMIG	0.27	0.23	1		
FDI	-0.04	-0.21	-0.06	1	
UNEM	0.48	-0.19	0.02	0.08	1

Source: Researchers' Computation.

The correlation matrix of the variables is as shown in Table 3 above. The correlation matrix is a statistical tool that measures the relationship between dependent and independent variables. It provides a table of correlation coefficients which describe the strength and direction of the linear relationships between each pair of variables. From the table above therefore, economic development proxied by HDI as a dependent variable has a positive correlation with independent variables NETMIG (0.27), POV (0.35), and UNEM (0.48). This therefore indicates that the variables tend to move in the same direction. Meanwhile, FDI has a weak negative correlation (-0.04) with the dependent variable.

4.2 Unit Root Test

The Augmented Dickey Fuller and the Philip-Perron unit root tests were conducted to examine the stationarity condition of the variables. As indicated in Table 4 below, FDI, POV, and NETMIG, were stationary at level in ADF, and PP, while HDI, UNEM, were stationary after first differencing in both ADF and PP. In other words, the variables are integrated of order zero and one (i.e., I (0) and I(1)). Where some of the variables are I (0) while others are I (1), this mix order of stationary at levels and first difference implies that an ARDL model is best suited for this analysis but a co-integration test is necessary to check if a long run relationship exists or not.

Table 4: ADF and Philip-Perron Unit Root Test Results

Variables	ADF		Order of integration	Level	PP	
	Level	1 st Difference			1 st Difference	Order of integration
HDI	-0.131999	-7.409909	I(1)	-	-	I(1)
POV	4.513346	-	I(0)	-	-	I(0)
NETMIG	-5.93119	-	I(0)	-	-	I(0)
UNEM	-0.456868		I(1)	-	-	I(1)
FDI	-4.042912		I(0)	-	-	I(0)

Source: Researchers' computation.

Note: Mackinnon critical values for ADF at 1, 5 and 10% levels are -3.60, -2.93 and -2.60 respectively, and for PP are 3.605, 2.936 and 2.606, respectively. ** means significant at 5% level.

4.3 Lag Length Selection

Table 5: Lag length criteria

Endogenous variables: HDI, FDI, NETMIG, UNEM, POV

Table 5: Lag Length Criteria

Lag	LogL	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0	-1156.282	NA	5.03e+19	59.55293	59.76621	59.62946
1	-1065.860	153.0230	1.78e+18	56.19792	57.47759*	56.65706
2	-1049.493	23.50087	2.95e+18	56.64066	58.98671	57.48240
3	-1035.203	16.85519	6.11e+18	57.18988	60.60231	58.41423
4	-953.2533	75.64552*	4.81e+17*	54.26940*	58.74822	55.87636*

Source: Researchers' computation.

The efficiency and validity of an error correction model depends on the lag structure. The study used VAR lag order selection criteria to determine the lag lengths. The study employed the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) and Schwarz Criterion (SC) and the result shows four optimal lag lengths in migration and economic development models as shown in Table 5 above. In order to reduce the possibilities of underestimation whilst maximizing the likelihood of recovering the true lag (Venus, 2004), the study used three and four as the maximum lag lengths, respectively.

Table 6: Co-Integration Test Results

5% critical value						
Equations	K	F-Stat	I (0)	I (1)	Outcome	
HDI (FDI, NETMIG, POV, UNEM)	4	2,655	2.86	4.01	Co-integration	

Note: K =number of parameters

Source: Researchers' computation.

4.1.4 Co-integration Test Results

From the bound testing result reported in Table 6 ab, long run relationship exists amongst the variables in all the estimated equations, given that the values of the F-statistic are greater than the critical values at five per cent level in both the upper and the lower bounds. Therefore, the null hypothesis of absence of co-integration is rejected, while the study proceeds to estimate the long run coefficient of each of the equations.

4.2 Findings, Presentation and Analysis of Econometric Results of migration and Human Development Index equation

Dependent variable: HDI

Table 6: ARDL Long Run Coefficient

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
POV	-0.000001	0.000000	2.897991	0.0325
NETMIG	0.000000	0.000000	0.610472	0.5501
FDI	0.011735	0.005201	2.256334	0.0270
UNEM	0.005499	0.001836	2.995574	0.0086
C	0.360190	0.019286	18.676201	0.0000

Source: Researchers' Computation.

Table 6 presents the long-run relationships between the dependent variable and its explanatory variables. The results indicate that Poverty (POV), Foreign Direct Investment (FDI), and Unemployment (UNEM) significantly influence the economic development. These variables have varying directions in sign and magnitudes of impact. Poverty (POV), has a coefficient of -0.000001 with a p -value of 0.0325, showing a statistically significant negative impact. This implies that a 1-unit increase in poverty leads to a 0.001%-unit decrease in the economic development, *ceteris paribus*. This finding is in line with a priori expectation and underscores the adverse effects of high poverty levels on economic development. The pervasive poverty during the review period reflected multidimensional deprivation, exacerbating socio-economic issues such as youth unemployment, restiveness, inflation, and insecurity.

Unemployment (UNEM) has a coefficient of 0.005499 with a p -value of 0.0086, showing it is statistically significant and a positive impact. This implies that a 1-unit increase in unemployment leads to a 0.05% increase in the economic development, *ceteris paribus*. This result does not conform with a priori expectation, suggesting that UNEM has a substantial impact on economic development in the long run during the period under review. This unexpected outcome suggests that unemployment, despite its adverse connotations, does not exert a meaningful influence on HDI over the long run.

Similarly, Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) also has a positive significant relationship, with a coefficient of 0.011735 and a p -value of 0.0270. This indicates that a 1-unit increase in FDI results in a 1.1% increase in the economic development. This result is in line with a priori expectation, and its significant relationship suggest that in the period under review, its contribution to economic development was positive.

The coefficient for net migration (NETMIG) is positive and statistically insignificant, indicating that a unit increase in NETMIG results in a 0% increase in HDI and an insignificant p -value of 0.5501. This finding is not in line with a priori expectation during the study period. The positive effect suggests that, within the period under review, net migration dynamics did not contribute to reduction and the attendance of negative impact on economic development. This finding is in line with the views of Faruk et al, (2022) whose findings revealed a negative significant long run relationship between net migration and economic development. The constant term(C) is also statistically significant, with a coefficient of 0.360190 and a p -value

of 0.0000, representing the baseline value of the dependent variable when all explanatory variables are zero.

In summary, the long-run analysis highlights the complex interplay between migration variables and economic development. While certain factors such as FDI, UNEM and POV positively influenced Economic Development, but NETMIG posed significant challenges. These findings underscore the need for targeted policy interventions to address structural issues to curb migration in Nigeria.

Table 8: Short run coefficients of migration and human development index equation result:

Dependent variable: HDI

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(HDI(-1))	-0.139869	0.230318	-0.607287	0.5522
D(HDI(-2))	0.276587	0.218003	1.268732	0.2227
D(HDI(-3))	-0.184569	0.163146	-1.131311	0.2746
D(POV)	0.000000	0.000000	1.754521	0.0985
D(POV(-1))	-0.000000	0.000000	-0.370458	0.7159
D(POV(-2))	-0.000000	0.000000	-1.934539	0.0709
D(POV(-3))	-0.000000	0.000000	2.173582	0.0451
D(NETMIG)	0.000000	0.000000	1.314971	0.2071
D(NETMIG(-1))	-0.000000	0.000000	-0.029429	0.9769
D(NETMIG(-2))	0.000000	0.000000	0.039068	0.9693
D(NETMIG(-3))	-0.000000	0.000000	-2.157274	0.0465
D(FDI)	-0.000109	0.001066	-0.102225	0.9198
D(FDI(-1))	0.002407	0.001108	-2.173589	0.0451
D(UNEM)	0.000899	0.000346	2.596946	0.0195
D(UNEM(-1))	-0.000747	0.000444	-1.682241	0.1119
D(UNEM(-2))	0.001456	0.000456	3.192299	0.0057
D(UNEM(-3))	-0.001357	0.000440	-3.087643	0.0071
CointEq(-1)	-0.125393	0.158110	-1.990999	0.0372
R-squared	0.992478	Mean dependent var		0.448462
Adjusted R-squared	0.982134	S.D. dependent var		0.047547
S.E. of regression	0.006355	Akaike info criterion		-6.990557
Sum squared resid	0.000646	Schwarz criterion		-6.009482
Log likelihood	159.3159	Hannan-Quinn criter.		-6.638555
F-statistic	95.95437	Durbin-Watson stat		2.770732
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

The short-run dynamics of the relationship between the Human Development Index (HDI) and migration are presented in Table 8. The first lag of Human Development Index (HDI (-1)) is insignificant, with a coefficient of -0.139869 and a p-value of 0.5522, which is higher

than the 0.05 threshold. This indicates that a 1-unit increase in lagged HDI (the previous year's value of HDI) leads to a 0.55-unit decrease in the current period's HDI, holding other factors constant (*ceteris paribus*). Similarly, the second lag of HDI (HDI (-2)) is also not significant, with a coefficient of 0.276587 and a p-value of 0.2227. This suggests that HDI from three previous years has no significant effect on current HDI.

In addition, the third lag of Poverty (POV (-3)) is statistically significant, with a coefficient of 1.79E-07 and a p-value of 0.0451. This implies that a unit increase in poverty from three years ago significantly increases HDI by 1.79- units in the short run. Among the controlled variables, the third lag of net migration (NETMIG (-3)) is significant, with a p-value of 0.0465. However, its coefficient is negative (-2.34E-08) indicating that a 1-unit increase NETMIG today would lead to a 1.79% reduction in economic development after three years, *ceteris paribus*.

The results indicate a negative and significant relationship between FDI and HDI in first period lag. Specifically, a unit increase in FDI results in a 0.02% increase in HDI, suggesting that FDI has a positive impact on economic development in the short run during the period under review. The coefficient of unemployment (UMEM) is negative and significantly related to HDI in first and third period lag, indicating that a unit rise in UNEM in both periods will lead to a -0.07% and -0.01% decrease in economic development respectively. These results of the first and third period lag align with theoretical expectations, indicating that unemployment rate exerts a major negative influence on HDI in the short run. The error correction mechanism (ECM) has the correct sign and magnitude; with a coefficient of -0.125393, this indicates that approximately 12.5% of short-run disequilibrium is corrected annually to restore long-run equilibrium. The p-value of 0.0372, its p-value is less than 5%, signifying its significance.

The R-squared value of 0.992478 and the adjusted R-squared value of 0.982134 suggest that approximately 99% of the variation in HDI is explained by the current and one-period lagged values of foreign direct investment, net migration, poverty, and unemployment. The remaining 1% is attributable to other factors not included in the model. The F-statistic value of 95.95 indicates that the explanatory variables collectively have a statistically significant impact on HDI, confirming the model's overall goodness-of-fit. Furthermore, the Durbin-Watson (D-W) statistic of 2.77 indicates the absence of autocorrelation and multicollinearity in the model, ensuring the reliability of the results for economic forecasting and policy formulation.

4.2 Discussion of Findings

From the long run and short run analysis of migration and economic development proxied by HDI, unemployment, showed a positive relationship with the dependent variable. This is in contravention to theoretical expectation except poverty, net migration, foreign direct investment, which is in line with *a priori* expectation. The contraventions of the above variables show that the null hypothesis will be rejected by showing that unemployment does not significantly impact economic development in the period under review. Whereas, the conformity of net migration, foreign direct investment to economic development is conformity with theoretical expectation and it shows that the alternate hypothesis will be accepted, suggesting that these variables has a significant effect on economic development in the period under review. This result is in line with the findings of Faruk et al, (2022) who revealed a

negative significant long run relationship between net migration and economic growth in his study on net migration and economic growth nexus: empirical evidence from Nigeria.

More so, positive, negative and significant relationships were found between poverty, foreign direct investment, and unemployment in both the short run and the long run periods. This varied proportion of relationship between these variables and economic development suggests that in the period under review the variables exhibited random variation having an overwhelming influence on the dependent variable. The positive effect of foreign direct investment, in both long and short run period shows the adverse effect of these two variables on economic development suggesting that the degree of foreign investment during the study period contributed to improvements in the nation's balance of payments, resulting in improve foreign and local investment thereby raising the investment portfolio of the nation.

Meanwhile, the positive effects of poverty and unemployment in both long and short run deviate from theoretical expectation, suggesting that although it was positive but their influence on economic development was minimal and therefore insufficient enough to bring about any positive contribution to economic development in the period under study. The positive relationship between UNEM and HDI implies that as unemployment rises, there is an accompanying impact on HDI. This relationship may reflect increased economic activity in sectors not immediately reducing unemployment, such as government interventions or social safety nets. Also, the magnitude and sign of net migration was in line with theoretical expectation and therefore had adverse effect on economic development.

5. Conclusion and Recommendation

The study examined the relationship between Migration and Economic Development in Nigeria from 1981-2023 adopting the autoregressive distributive lag model. The study observed that changes in Migration variables affect economic development in Nigeria. In addition, the study revealed a negative relationship between net migration and economic development proxy by human development index. Lastly, from our findings, net migration, high poverty rate, and high unemployment rate will lead to a reduction in economic development in Nigeria.

Recommendation

(i)The public authority should implement targeted migration policies to address specific needs of the country by improving infrastructural provision such as electricity, good roads, adequate pipe borne water etc.

(ii)The public authority should invest and bring education closer to the people by citing educational institutions in the rural areas and not concentrating them in the urban centres. This and human training will increase human capital of the workforce.

(iii)The study recommends that government should improve on working conditions and wages to reduce the pull factor of better job opportunities.

iv) Government through the Federal Ministry of Labour and Employment, in collaboration with the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), should implement labour-market-oriented programs targeting skill development and employment growth. A pilot initiative should begin within the

next 12 months, emphasizing sectors with high employment elasticity such as agriculture and manufacturing.

v) Government should establish suitable industries in various areas. Specifically, agro-industries and integrated agriculture is a must so as to fully engage rural dwellers, as this will play a significant role to increasing aggregate economic activity with the resultant positive multiplier effects. Social amenities/infrastructure such as good road network, electricity, pipe borne water, equipped health centers, recreation facilities, among others need to be urgently addressed, especially in the rural areas and critical sectors.

Suggestion for further studies

Given that urban migration and economic development is a broad concept, subsequent studies in this area should be done by introducing different explanatory variables to determine their individual impact on economic development. This will be necessary to see if the findings in this study will be replicated. This study should also be replicated in other African countries that experience capital formation crisis like Nigeria for comparative analysis.

References

- Abah, N. (2010). *Development Administration: A Multi – Dispensary Approach*. Enugu: John Jacob Classic Publishers.
- Adaja, O.V and Olajide, O. E. (2022). Harnessing The Migration and Development Nexus for Sustainable Development in Nigeria. *Nigerian Community Development Journal Vol.11 June 2021. Pp 111 – 127*.
- Adeseye, A. (2021). The Effect of Migrants Remittance on Economy Growth in Nigeria: An Empirical Study. *Open Journal of Political Science, 11, 99-122*.
- Adewale, J. G. (2005). Socio-economic factors associated with urban-rural migration in Nigeria: A case study of Oyo State, Nigeria. *Journal of Human Ecology, 17(1), 13-16*.
- Ajadi, T. O. (2010). Private Universities in Nigeria- The Challenges Ahead. *American Journal of Scientific Research, 7: 15-24*.
- Adejogbe, M. A. (Ed.). (2004). *Industrialization, Urbanization and Development in Nigeria: 1950-99*. Concept Publications.
- Akpoko, S., & Adefila, J. (2014). Role of rural-ward migration in economic development in Jos South Area of Plateau State Nigeria. *Research on Humanities and Social Sciences, 4(20)*.
- Barke, M., & O'Hare, G. (1991). The Third World–Conceptual Frameworks in. *Geography*.
- Castles, S., & R. Delgado Wise (eds.). 2008. *Migration and Development: Perspectives from the South*. International Organization for Migration (IOM), Geneva.
- Comfort, C. (2012). Vocational technical education in Nigeria: Challenges and the way forward. *Business Management Dynamics, 2(6), 1*.
- Delgado-Wise, R., & L. Guarnizo. 2007. *Migration and Development: Lessons from the Mexican Experience*. Feature Story, Migration Policy Institute.

- Deshingkar, P., & S. Grimm. 2005. International Migration and Development: A Global Perspective. Migration Research Series, No. 19, International Organization for Migration, Geneva.
- Duru, I. U. (2021). Examination of the causes and consequences of international migration in Nigeria. *Asian Development Policy Review*, 9(4), 180-193.
- Gimba, Z., & Kumshe, M. G. (2011). Causes and effects of rural-urban migration in Borno State: A Case Study of Maiduguri Metropolis. *Asian Journal of Business and Management Sciences*, 1(1), 168-172.
- Gmelch, G., & Zenner, W.P. (1996). *Urban life: Reading in the anthropology of the city*. (4th ed.). Illinois: Waveland press, INC.
- Harris, J. R., & Todaro, M. P. (1970). Migration, unemployment and development: a two-sector analysis. *The American economic review*, 60(1), 126-142.
- Hussain, S., Siddiqui, B. N., & HASSAN, M. Z. Y. (2004). A sociological study of factors responsible for migration: a case study of Faisalabad city (Pakistan). *Education*, 32.
- Imevbore, A. M. A. (2002). On Overview of the contribution of Industry to sustainable development in Nigeria. *A Report Prepared for Unido for The Rio*, 10.
- Ismail, A. (2019). Socio-developmental appraisal of rural-urban migration in rural community of Nigeria. *International journal of social science and economic research*, 4(6), 4613-4636.
- Johnson, K. E., & Ifeoma, U. (2018). Rural development as a panacea for rural–urban migration in Nigeria. *Art Human Open Acc J*, 2(5), 241-244.
- Kunwar, L. S. (2021). Impacts of Migration on Poverty Reduction: A Critical Analysis. *Journal of Population and Development*, 92-103.
- Lee, E. S. (1966). A theory of migration. *Demography*, 3(1), 47-57.
- Lall, S. V., Selod, H., & Shalizi, Z. (2006). *Rural-urban migration in developing countries: A survey of theoretical predictions and empirical findings*. The World Bank. Abuja, Nigeria.
- Massey D.S., Arango J., Hugo G., Kouaouci A., Pellegrino A. and Taylor J.E. (1993). Theories of International Migration: a Review and Appraisal. *Population and Development Review*, 19, pp. 431-466.
- Negari W, and Mishra, M. K. (2019), Impact of Rural-Urban migration on Economic growth of rural Ethiopia. *Amity Journal of Management*, Vol. VII, Vol 1
- Nyagba, S. (2009). Review of the Nigerian rural development policy for sustainable growth. In *A paper presentation at the West African Regional Conference on Smart, appropriate technologies for rural communities*.
- Ratha, D., Mohapatra, S., & Scheja, E. (2014). Impact of Migration on Economic and Social Development in Sub-Saharan African countries: A Review of Evidence and Emerging Issues. Policy Research Working Paper 5558, 1-40.

- Škuflić, L. & Vučković, V. (2018). The effect of emigration on unemployment rates: the case of EU emigrant countries, *Economic Research-Ekonomska Istraživanja*, 31(1), 1826-1836.
- Troshchenkov, S. (2011). Influence of immigration on the unemployment rate: The case of Denmark. *Journal of Economic Surveys*, 22(1), 1, 1-30.
- Ojo, O. (2016). The impact of immigration on Nigerian Economy. *Journal of Labor Economics*, 4(1), 134-149.
- Todaro, M. P. (1976). Internal migration in developing countries: a review of theory, evidence, methodology and research priorities. International Labour Office, Geneva.